

Mobile Phone App Data for Understanding Urban Public Park Usage: Opportunities and Challenges

Luning Li^{*1,2}, Michael Sinclair^{†1,2}

¹ Division of Urban Studies and Social Policy, University of Glasgow, Glasgow, UK

² Urban Big Data Centre, University of Glasgow, Glasgow, UK

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Summary

This study explores the use of mobile phone app data, a novel form of mobile data, to analyze urban public park usage, addressing limitations in traditional data collection methods. By leveraging two independent MPA datasets from the Glasgow City Region over a three-year period, we developed a practical framework to estimate park visitation and identify spatial patterns of park use across different socio-demographic groups. Preliminary findings highlight MPA data's potential for providing scalable, highly granular insights into park usage, while also revealing inherent challenges. The methodology, though focused on parks, is extendable to other natural spaces, offering valuable tools for equitable and sustainable urban planning.

KEYWORDS: Mobile phone application data, Urban public park, Mobility, Big data, Geospatial

1. Introduction

Urban public parks play crucial roles in fostering sustainable, healthy, and socially equitable urban environments (Lee & Maheswaran, 2011, Loures et al., 2007, Xiao et al., 2017). While understanding how these spaces are used and valued is crucial for urban planning and management, such data remain scarce and challenging to collect (Heikinheimo et al., 2020). Traditional data collection methods, such as household surveys based on random sampling, often demand significant resources and have inherent limitations. These approaches become particularly challenging during events like COVID-19, as their limited sample sizes and delayed response times impede detailed spatial and temporal resolution for understanding human mobility (Sinclair et al., 2023). Over the recent decade, social media has become an alternative approach for understanding the use of nature (Wood et al., 2013, Heikinheimo et al., 2020). Social media images and posts, along with their geo-tagged locations, offer valuable fine-scale data on human interactions with natural populations, ecosystems, and biomes. However, the active data collection methods inherent to social media can introduce biases and raised concerns regarding how accurately the social media data portrays reality.

An emerging opportunity exists in mobile phone app (MPA) data, which provides near real-time observations of peoples' nuanced movement. Passively collected through multiple approaches including GPS, Bluetooth, and Wi-Fi, it captures much wider and highly granular spatial and temporal information of human activities than social media (Gibbs et al., 2023). These advantages suggest its superior potential for modeling visitation compared to other forms of digital mobility data. To date, this data has been used for monitoring overall travel flows (Wang et al., 2019a, Zhang et al., 2023, Mavrogeni et al., 2024) as well as individual transport behaviors (Vanky et al., 2017), understanding neighborhood diversity (Xu et al., 2022) and disparity (Trasberg & Cheshire, 2023). Beyond these applications, MPA data have the potentials to enhance our understanding of pressing societal challenges, especially in domains like urban planning, service accessibility, and social equity (Mavrogeni et al., 2024, Matthews et al., 2023, Trasberg & Cheshire, 2023).

* Luning.Li@glasgow.ac.uk

† Michael.Sinclair@glasgow.ac.uk

Despite its significant potential, the application of MPA data in understanding human engagement with natural environments (e.g., park use) remains limited. Critical barriers include restricted access to raw datasets (Monz et al., 2019; Winder et al., 2025), unresolved ethical concerns such as privacy risks (de Montjoye et al., 2020), questions around data representativeness (Gibbs et al., 2023; Trasberg & Cheshire, 2023), and challenges in comparing performance across different data vendors (Winder et al., 2025). To date, few efforts have successfully addressed these methodological and ethical challenges. As a result, the substantial potential of MPA data for estimating human visitation to natural spaces remains largely untapped due to the lack of a rigorous analytical framework.

2. Objectives

This study presents a practical methodological framework for using MPA data in estimating nature-based visitation. Taking urban public parks as a study case, we focus on addressing two key research questions: (1) What insights can MPA data reveal about urban public park usage? (2) What are the advantages, potential applications, and limitations of MPA data in studying urban public park usage? The analysis draws upon two comprehensive, independent datasets, each spanning three years of observations across the Glasgow City Region, Scotland. By examining dimensions of park usage between these datasets – (1) visitor sociodemographics, (2) visitation estimates, and (3) spatial patterns of park use – we aim to advance the understanding of both opportunities and challenges in using MPA data for nature-based visitation analysis, while expanding the methodological toolkit available for human-nature interaction research.

3. Methodology

Figure 1 illustrates the analytical framework employed in this study. We utilize two extensive and independent datasets from Huq and Tamoco, each spanning three years (2019–2021) and covering the Glasgow City Region. This region includes the core Glasgow City, the largest city in Scotland, and seven surrounding local councils. Using the latest 2024 boundary shapefiles from Open Street Map, we identified 392 public parks and gardens (hereafter referred to as "parks") within this area (Figure 2). Following the methodology proposed by Sinclair et al. (2023), we estimated the home Datazone for each mobile phone user. This allowed us to link users to the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD, <https://simd.scot/>) quintile of their home Datazone, providing insights into their socio-demographic characteristics. We then only focused on mobile data points falling within the park boundaries (Figure 3).

To enhance the representativeness of the mobile user data, we calculated weights for users from different councils and SIMD quintiles by comparing the distribution of mobile users to the adult population distribution. Annual population estimates for this purpose were obtained from the [National Records of Scotland](#) for the years 2019 through 2021. The adult population was calculated as the total population minus individuals under the age of 16. Notably, the opportunistic nature of mobile data collection introduces temporal inconsistencies that complicate longitudinal analysis. This study addresses these challenges through implementation of a dynamic weighting framework accounting for demographic shifts and technological adoption patterns. We scaled up the monthly proportion of mobile users visiting parks to estimate the actual number of visits, using the adult population as a baseline. Building on this foundation, our analysis of public park usage patterns encompasses three key dimensions: (1) visitor sociodemographics, (2) visitation estimates, and (3) spatial patterns of park use.

Figure 1. Analytical framework for employing MPA data to analyze park use

Figure 2 Glasgow City Region, council areas, and public parks (N=392)

Figure 3. (a) The number of unique mobile users with assigned home Datazones and SIMD quintiles, and (b) the mean number of MPA datapoints per user within parks.

4. Preliminary Findings and Discussion

Our analysis reveals patterns in MPA data representation across both the Huq and Tamoco datasets (Figure 4). Geographically, some councils exhibit consistent patterns of over- or under-representation. For instance, West Dunbartonshire and Renfrewshire consistently show over-representation across both datasets throughout 2019-2021. In contrast, other councils such as East Dunbartonshire and East Renfrewshire demonstrate varying patterns of representation across datasets. Sociodemographic patterns also exhibit notable variations. In the 2019 Tamoco data, individuals from more deprived quintiles (1 and 2) are overrepresented, while those from less deprived quintiles (4 and 5) show underrepresentation. However, this pattern varies across datasets. The mobile phone sample weight, which combines geographic and sociodemographic weights, reveals more complex dynamics, as Figure 5 illustrates their temporal variation across the study period. These variations reflect underlying changes in the scale and volume of MPA data collection in both datasets. Such inherent changes underscore the importance of our mobile phone sample weighting method in ensuring balanced representation of mobile users across both geographic areas and sociodemographic groups relative to the adult population.

Figure 4. Geographic, sociodemographic, and mobile phone sample weights for Huq and Tamoco datasets

Figure 5. Variation of mobile phone sample weights

Based on this, we calculated the annual visits to all parks group by different councils. Figure 6 shows the results for each year. In general, the Huq and Tamoco estimates show similar patterns in park visitation across Councils over the three years, with Glasgow City consistently recording the highest visits and East Dunbartonshire showing the lowest. These estimates of Huq and Tamoco are highly correlated, indicating this consistent trend over time. Figure 7 shows the changes in ranks of parks based on their annual visitation. Although the same park may have different rankings in Huq and Tamoco data over the three years, 9 out of top 10 parks are the same between the two datasets. Figure 8 shows the potential of mapping spatial patterns of park use from different sociodemographic groups.

Figure 6. Annual park visitation group by home Councils

Figure 7. Bump charts illustrating the changes in annual visitation rankings for parks from 2019 to 2021, based on (a) Huq and (b) Tamoco datasets.

Figure 8. Visitor datapoints in Glasgow Green group by SIMD quintiles based on Huq dataset (2019-2021)

Despite promising results, this study identifies several methodological challenges using the MPA data. First, the absence of field validation data limits our ability to assess estimation accuracy. Second, fluctuations in user numbers and datapoints due to potential changes in business agreements and privacy policies complicate temporal analyses. These limitations represent ongoing areas of development in our proposed framework.

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Biographies

Luning Li is a Research Associate in Urban Analytics at Urban Big Data Centre, University of Glasgow. Her primary research interests are leveraging novel data sources to understand human mobility in urban contexts.

Michael Sinclair is a Lecturer in Urban Analytics at the Urban Big Data Centre, University of Glasgow. His interests focus on the growing potential and challenges of new forms of user generated data for social and environmental research. He is currently the PI on two projects focussing on these issues.